

2. Seasonal variation in CH₄ emissions from an unfertilized irrigated ricefield in Vercelli, Italy.

primarily by gas bubbles. Plant-mediated transport is the dominant pathway during Jul and Aug.

High diurnal variations in rates were observed during EVP (values between 0 and 30 mg/m² per h). These changes correlated well with changes in soil temperature. On a seasonal average, 0.28 g CH₄ was emitted/m² per day, resulting in a total emission of about 33 g CH₄/m² during the vegetative phase.

On the basis of this value, we estimate the global annual CH₄ emission from ricefields to range between 50 and 150 million tons. Thus, flooded ricefields may be the most important individual source of atmospheric methane, contributing about 25% of the total annual CH₄ emission. Further field measurements in the major rice-growing areas of South and Southeast Asia are needed to better estimate global emission of CH₄ from ricefields. ■

Agroecological zoning of the Red River plain region, Vietnam

Cao Liem, Dao Chau Thu, and Tran Tu Nga, University of Agriculture NI, Hanoi, Vietnam

The Red River plain (about 15,000 km²) is one of two main rice-producing regions of Vietnam. Altitude is less than 25 m above sea level, with relatively flat topography. Soil is primarily Red River alluvial. The climate is monsoon tropical with a cold winter. Current population density is the highest in Vietnam: more than 500 inhabitants/km².

The region has diversified cropping systems: rice, maize, peanut, tuber crops, and short-duration industrial crops. The rice crop is essential.

We have been working on agroecological zoning of the Red River plain region.

The objective is, first, to divide the Red River plain region into ecosystems that have

- the same main soil class, meso-macorelief type, and water regime,
- the same main cropping systems,
- the same trends in land use, crop protection, and yield improvement.

Agrosystem zones in the Red River Delta, Vietnam.

Zone	Name of the zone	Area (km ²)	Topography	Water regime	Cropping pattern	Solution
I	The alluvial zone outside the Red River Dike	48,000	High	Seasonal flood	Legume - maize Vegetable - maize Sugarcane	Seasonal occupation
II	The high alluvial bank of the Red River	172,000	High to middle	Relatively suitable	Rice - rice - maize Rice - rice - potato Rice - rice - vegetables Sugarcane - jute	More effective cropping pattern
III	The low gley alluvial zone in the Red River Delta	499,000	Low	High ground water table	Rice - rice	Intersification of rice crop
IV	The Thaibinh River alluvial zone	183,600	Middle to low	Unsustainable	Rice - rice	Fertilizer and water management
V	The Hanamninh alluvial lowlands	103,200	Low	Flooded year-round	Rice - fallow Rice - rice	Drainage, liming, phosphorus fertilizer and flood-tolerant varieties
VI	The seashore saline alluvial zone	104,500	Low	Seasonal	Mangrove: flooded Rush: mean saline Rice - food crops in less saline	Salt washing and salt-tolerant varieties of rice
VII	The acid salt alluvial zone	158,400	Middle to low	Seasonal Al ³⁺ toxic	Rice - rice Rice - tobacco Rice - vegetable	Sulfate acid washing, liming and phosphorus fertilizer Variety improvement
VIII	The depleted grey soil zone	194,200	Terraced	Waterstress	Rice - rice - legume Rice - potato Rice - rice - vegetables Rice - mung - maize	Water management intensification

Next is to divide the ecosystems into subecosystems with some interchange of ecological factors (by cropping system).

On the basis of these criteria, we have divided the Red River plain region into eight ecosystems (see table and figure). ■